

Exploring Discrepancies in Magnetic Resonance Imaging Understanding: A Qualitative Investigation among the General Population

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Abstract

Background: In modern healthcare, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) serves as a cornerstone diagnostic tool, yet public misconceptions surrounding its use persist. This study utilizes qualitative methods to investigate MRI misconceptions among the public, aiming to understand attitudes and identify common misconceptions. Recognizing these perceptions is crucial for enhancing patient education and healthcare communication.

Objective: To identify and explore prevalent misconceptions among the general population regarding Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI).

Methodology: The research was conducted in Brainware University's Allied Health Sciences including students and general public using a validated questionnaire. The study included 271 respondents excluding BMRIT students and interns. The questionnaire addressed demographics and MRI knowledge and false perceptions.

Result: Among all the participants, 54 exhibit excellent knowledge of MRI, while 158 demonstrate good understanding. However, 51 individuals show insufficient knowledge, and 8 possess poor knowledge regarding MRI.

Conclusion: By addressing misconceptions, anxiety and fear during MRI procedures can be minimized, enhancing overall healthcare experiences. Furthermore, dispelling myths surrounding MRI promotes its appropriate utilization, optimizing healthcare resources and ultimately improving patient outcomes.

Keywords: Magnetic Resonance Imaging, perception, equipment, public, Claustrophobia,

INTRODUCTION

In modern clinical medicine, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) stands as a pivotal diagnostic tool. Patient comprehension of MRI procedures is essential for enhancing efficiency, ensuring patient comfort and safety, and optimizing time management within MRI departments. [1] Described a century ago as "the most significant advancement in medical diagnosis since the discovery of the x-ray," MRI has evolved into a cornerstone of contemporary radiology. Utilizing radio waves, magnetism, and computational processing, MRI generates detailed images of bodily structures, rooted in the principle of Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR). [2] The inaugural human MRI scan took place in 1997, producing a single image over a five-hour period. MRI technology, non-invasive in nature,

provides intricate three-dimensional anatomical images, aiding in disease detection, diagnosis, and treatment monitoring. By leveraging the behaviour of protons within water molecules in living tissues under a magnetic field, MRI identifies atoms, making it a valuable diagnostic tool [3]. The inception of MRI dates back to July 3, 1977, marking the first live human patient examination. Building upon physicist I. I. Rabi's pioneering work in the 1930s on monitoring the magnetic properties of atomic nuclei, MRI has become an indispensable, life-saving medical procedure for imaging internal body structures and facilitating medical diagnosis [4]. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) technology stands as a significant achievement in modern medical diagnostics, fundamentally altering how healthcare professionals perceive and grasp the intricacies of the human body [5]. Despite its wide adoption and proven efficacy in diagnosing various medical conditions, there exists a prevailing cloud of misunderstanding and unease surrounding MRI equipment among the general population. This qualitative inquiry delves deeply into these misconceptions, aiming to unravel the intricate web of false beliefs that envelop the MRI experience for many individuals. MRI machines, with their imposing appearance and the enigmatic workings of their technology, often instil anxiety and apprehension in those undergoing scans [6]. These emotions stem largely from a lack of understanding and misinformation regarding the safety, purpose, and functionality of the technology. Recognizing the importance of pinpointing the underlying causes of these misconceptions is paramount, as they can obstruct individuals from seeking necessary medical care, intensify anxiety during imaging procedures, and erode trust in healthcare providers. By shedding light on these false perceptions, our goal is to bridge the gap between public understanding and the genuine essence of MRI technology, enabling informed decision-making and dispelling unwarranted fears surrounding this vital diagnostic tool. Through thorough interviews and qualitative analysis, we explore the varied spectrum of beliefs, concerns, and experiences that shape individuals' viewpoints on MRI equipment [7]. By amplifying these narratives, we aim to uncover common misconceptions, challenge preconceived notions, and provide insights that can guide patient education efforts and improve communication between healthcare providers and the communities they serve [8].

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

Aim: To assess the false perceptions of general public towards the magnetic resonance imaging equipment in radiology department.

Objective:

- Investigate the level of understanding and awareness regarding Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) among the general population.
- Explore potential gaps or misconceptions in the public's knowledge of MRI technology.
- Identify common misunderstandings or areas of confusion related to MRI procedures and its implications.
- Examine factors influencing individuals' comprehension of MRI, including educational background, prior exposure, and sources of information.
- Assess public perceptions and attitudes towards MRI, including any fears, concerns, or beliefs that may affect their understanding or acceptance of the technology.

METHODOLOGY:

A prospective study was conducted among Allied Health Sciences students in between February 20 to March 20, 2024 at Brainware University in Barasat, Kolkata, West Bengal. The study involved collection of data via a self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of 20 questions, which was earlier validated by multiple subject expertise and approved by the School of Medical and Allied Health Sciences, Brainware University. The questionnaire was distributed among all the students of Allied Health Sciences out of which 272 responded to the survey. Those students who never studied MRI and subjected to MRI were included in the study. All students of Medical Radiology and Imaging Technology (MRIT) and Intern were not included in this study. The participant's identity was kept anonymous. Before participating in the survey, a clear instruction was given to the participants about the purpose of the study. The questionnaire was divided into three sections: A, B and C. Section A dealt with demographic information such as age, gender and programme. Section B and C included multiple choice question questions to assess participants' knowledge and perception on Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI).

Data Analysis:

The collected data was analysed using Microsoft excel. Descriptive statistics were used to analyse the demographic information and participants responses from different sections of the questionnaire. Microsoft Excel's charting features were utilized to create visual representations of key findings, enhancing the clarity and communicability of results.

Results:

The findings of this study are presented in three parts. They are Socio demographic characteristics of the participants, knowledge regarding MRI and perception of MRI. association between knowledge regarding MRI and its safety and socio demographic characteristics of patient and association between knowledge regarding MRI and its safety and patient's perception of scan. In this study, there were total 271 participants (154 male and 117 female) with mean age of 20.6 years (**Figure 1**). Similarly, majority (255, 94%) were found in age group of 18 years to 24 years while (15, 5.5%) were found in age group of 25 to 30 years and 1 (0.36%) were found in the age group of 31 to 35 years.

Knowledge regarding MRI

Among all the participants, 54 exhibit excellent knowledge of MRI, while 158 demonstrate good understanding. However, 51 individuals show insufficient knowledge, and 8 possess poor knowledge regarding MRI (**Figure 2**).

Second question was to assess the use of MRI details where most of the respondents (n=246, 92.1%) answered that MRI creates detailed images of the body's internal structures while, few (n= 11, 4.1%) of them reported that MRI produces sound waves and (n=10, 3.7%) reported that MRI produces x-rays (**Figure 3**). Third question was to assess the parts of MRI machine where majority (n=204,76.4%) of them answered x-ray tubes while few (n=41, 15.4%) of them reported that gradient coils are not a component of MRI machine and (n=12, 4.5%) reported Magnet is not a component of MRI machine while (n=10, 3.7%) reported that radiofrequency coils are not a part of MRI machine (**Figure 4**). Fourth question was to assess the advantage of MRI over other modalities where majority (n=166,62.6%) of them answered better soft tissue resolution while few (n=78, 29.4%) of them answered higher resolution,

very few (n=19, 7.2%) responded fast time scan is the best advantage and least (n=2, 0.8%) reported that lower cost (**Figure 5**).

Common Perceptions on MRI

This section was to assess false perception towards MRI. First question was to understand the primary reason for false perceptions about MRI scans where majority (n=206, 76%) of them answered lack of awareness, misinformation and Fear of unknown while, few (n= 38, 14%) of them reported that lack of awareness about MRI, very few (n=23, 8.5%) reported that misinformation and least (n=4, 1.5%) responded fear of unknown as the false perception towards MRI (**Figure 6**). Second question was to assess the MRI friendly metal in which majority (n=226, 83.4%) answered titanium while, others had lack of knowledge as they reported Aluminium, iron and brass as friendly metal (**Figure 7**).

It was accounted that, maximum participants (n=223, 82.3%) had a knowledge on claustrophobia while others (n= 48, 17.7%) did not have (**Figure 8**).

Less than half of the participants (n=114, 42.1%) responded that MRI scan cannot be performed on a patient with a metallic implant while (n=96, 35.4%) were having an assumption that the scan can be performed without any damage and the remaining (n= 61, 22.5%) were not sure. (**Figure 9**).

Moreover among the 271 participants surveyed, there was a question aimed at evaluating whether MRI scans are deemed safe for pregnant women, following which the highest number of participants (n=163, 60.1%) related with the pregnant females stage of pregnancy and medical necessity, other group of participants (n=49, 18.15%) marked MRI as a safe modality, a number of participants (n=49, 18.1) commented MRI as unsafe and a least number (n=10, 3.7%) of participants were unaware (**Figure 10**). Among 271 participants majority (n=135, 49.8%) of them think in MRI they only use ionizing radiations while (n=66, 24.4) reported that MRI is only used for brain studies while (n=50, 18.5%) reported that MRI causes pain. while few (n=20, 7.4%) participants think MRI is invasive (**Figure 11**).

As the study progressed, a question was introduced regarding whether children undergo MRI scans. Out of the 271 participants, the majority (n=123, 45.4%) reported using music as their coping strategy, while some (n= 77 ,28.4%) mentioned sleeping as their preferred method. A smaller group of participants (n=45, 16.6%) stated that children do not undergo MRI scans, and a minority (n=26, 9.6%) mentioned deep breathing as a coping strategy for children during scanning (**Figure 12**).

Excellent knowledge	Good knowledge	Insufficient knowledge	Poor knowledge
54 (19.9%)	158 (58.30)	51 (18.8%)	8 (2.95%)

Table-01

MEN & WOMEN PARTICIPANTS

Figure-01

KNOWLEDGE RATIO AMONG DIFFERENT GROUPS

Figure-02

PURPOSE OF MRI MACHINE

Figure-03
COMPONENT OF MRI MACHINE

Figure-04

ADVANTAGE OF MRI OVER OTHER MODALITIES

Figure-05

FALSE PERCEPTION ABOUT MRI

Figure-06

MRI FRIENDLY METAL

Figure-07

TYPES OF CLAUSTROPHOBIA

Figure-08

METALLIC IMPLANT SCAN IN MRI

Figure-09

SCAN OF PREGNANT FEMALE IN MRI

Figure-10

FALSE BELIEFS ABOUT MRI

■ They use ionizing radiation ■ only used for brain study ■ invasive ■ cause pain

Figure-11

STRATEGY FOR CHILDREN UNDERGO MRI SCAN

Figure-12

Discussion:

Medical imaging technologies like Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) have revolutionized modern healthcare by offering a non-invasive method to view internal bodies structures. Despite its proven effectiveness and widespread use, MRI is often subject to misunderstandings among the general public. One prevalent misconception about MRI is the belief that it exposes patients to harmful radiation. Unlike X-rays or CT scans, which use ionizing radiation, MRI relies on magnetic fields and radio waves for imaging, thus reducing the risks associated with radiation exposure. [9] As a result, MRI is considered a safer option, especially for repeated imaging studies. Another misconception concerns the fear that metal implants or objects in the body may shift or heat up during MRI procedures due to the strong magnetic fields involved. However, modern MRI machines are equipped with safety features to address these concerns. Patients undergo thorough screening before an MRI to identify any metallic objects that could pose a risk. In most cases, materials like titanium, which are non-ferromagnetic, are deemed safe for MRI. Additionally, strict control over magnetic field strength ensures the safety of patients with metal implants. Despite its effectiveness, MRI is not infallible, and its accuracy relies on the interpretation of trained radiologists. Some individuals mistakenly believe that MRI always provides definitive and accurate diagnoses. However, like any medical test, MRI has limitations, leading to the possibility of false positives or negatives. In a study conducted by Magbool Alelyani et al., examining perceptions and attitudes towards magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) safety, it was found that the education level of healthcare workers did not significantly influence their perception of MRI safety. However, the study revealed that nurses had a significantly higher knowledge

score regarding MRI safety compared to dentists, physicians, and laboratory specialists (p -value = 0.005). Conversely, the attitude score did not exhibit significant differences based on gender, age, profession, or education level of the participants (p -value > 0.05). These findings underscore the importance of training and advanced studies for healthcare workers to enhance their understanding and attitudes towards MRI safety. While the overall knowledge of MRI safety and procedures is deemed satisfactory, the study suggests the necessity for more comprehensive health education programs to further improve knowledge levels. [10] In a study conducted by Shrestha and Khadka et al., the assessment of patients' knowledge, perception, and safety regarding MRI scan revealed significant findings. A majority, comprising 85.5% of patients, mistakenly believed that MRI utilizes harmful ionizing radiation similar to CT scans and radiography. Interestingly, around 43 patients who believed MRI could aid in treating diseases also reported a decrease in pain post-MRI scan. Notably, these patients predominantly fell within the age group of 25 to 50 years. Furthermore, the study indicated that 26.8% of patients experienced claustrophobia and anxiety during the scan, with 13 patients having a history of previous MRI scans. The reduction in pain was particularly notable in responses related to diagnosis and treatment. Overall, a significant proportion of patients reported experiencing anxiety and claustrophobia during MRI scans. Assessing patient knowledge, perception, and safety concerning MRI scans holds potential to enhance patient compliance and optimize scan efficiency. [11] In a separate study by Dhafer M Alahmari et al., focusing on the perception and knowledge of MRI safety, the study encompassed a sample of 200 patients out of 230 surveys distributed in Saudi Arabia, with a response rate of approximately 87%. Analysis of the chi-square statistical test revealed significant associations (p -value=0.006) between age and gender, as well as the level of knowledge regarding MRI safety issues. Additionally, a notable significance (p -value=0.042) was observed between patients' knowledge levels and their educational attainment and annual income. Furthermore, a highly significant correlation (p -value<0.001) was identified between individuals' education levels or prior experiences and their inclination to seek information about MRI safety. These findings underscore the multifaceted influences shaping patients' perceptions and understanding of MRI safety, highlighting the importance of tailored educational interventions and outreach strategies. [12]

In our study we made assumptions regarding false perceptions towards MRI, it is found that knowledge on MRI Participants were queried regarding the radiation types employed in MRI, CT scans, and radiography. The majority (78.4%) correctly identified that MRI utilizes non-ionizing radiation, while a smaller fraction (21.6%) erroneously believed MRI does not involve ionizing radiation. In terms of MRI's imaging capabilities, a vast majority (92.1%) acknowledged its ability to generate detailed images of internal body structures. However, a small percentage (4.1%) incorrectly attributed MRI's function to producing sound waves, with an even smaller portion (3.7%) believing it emits x-rays.

Regarding the components of an MRI machine, most participants (76.4%) correctly identified x-ray tubes as integral parts. Nevertheless, there were misconceptions, with some participants mistakenly asserting that gradient coils (15.4%), magnets (4.5%), or radiofrequency coils (3.7%) are not components of an MRI machine. When queried about the advantages of MRI compared to other modalities, the majority (62.6%) recognized its superior soft tissue resolution. Fewer respondents cited higher resolution (29.4%), faster scan time (7.2%), or lower cost (0.8%) as advantages. However, a significant proportion of participants (49.8%) incorrectly believed that MRI exclusively involves ionizing radiation. Additionally, a notable

number assumed MRI is exclusively used for brain studies (24.4%), causes discomfort (18.5%), or is invasive (7.4%). The majority of participants (76%) attributed misconceptions about MRI to factors like lack of awareness, misinformation, and fear of the unknown. In contrast, fewer participants mentioned lack of awareness (14%), misinformation (8.5%), and fear of the unknown (1.5%). Regarding MRI-friendly metals, most (83.4%) correctly identified titanium, while some mentioned aluminium, iron, and brass due to lack of knowledge. While most participants (82.3%) were aware of claustrophobia, less than half (42.1%) believed MRI scans cannot be performed on patients with metallic implants. Some participants believed the scan could be done without damage (35.4%), while others were uncertain (22.5%). Concerning MRI safety for pregnant women, the majority (60.1%) acknowledged the importance of considering pregnancy stage and medical necessity. Some considered MRI safe (18.15%), while others deemed it unsafe (18.1%), and a few were unaware (3.7%). Regarding children undergoing MRI scans, most (45.4%) reported using music as a coping strategy, followed by sleeping (28.4%). Some participants thought children don't undergo MRI scans (16.6%), while a minority mentioned deep breathing as a coping strategy (9.6%).

Conclusion:

Misconceptions about MRI can heighten patient anxiety, leading to reluctance in undergoing vital diagnostic tests, potentially delaying treatment. Misinterpretation of MRI results due to misconceptions may result in unnecessary worry or inappropriate medical decisions. To address this, clear communication, patient education, and public awareness are vital. Healthcare providers must debunk MRI myths, ensuring patients understand its safety and benefits. Public awareness campaigns should disseminate accurate information via various channels. By fostering understanding and trust in MRI, patients can make informed decisions, facilitating timely diagnosis and treatment, thus improving overall healthcare outcomes.

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